

OCRE

Online Coins of the Roman Empire

MANUAL: MAKING THE MASS MANAGEABLE

Using OCRE as a tool for the study of Roman coinage

Sven Betjes (Radboud University) – sven.betjes@ru.nl – June 2024

*Arco di Severo, e Caracalla. A Forami per sostegno
di bronzo. B Tempio della Concordia
Cavata del Tempio di Giove Tonante. D Colon-
na rimasa in piedi della Grecoetarsi.
Francesi Architetto dis. inc.*

N.B. the guide below is made for MS Excel 2016, so that for other versions of Excel certain functions may be a little different. This guide can also be used for the online databases that belong to the same project as OCRE, see: <http://nomisma.org/datasets>.

Step 1: Entering the world of Roman imperial coinage

1. Go to: <http://numismatics.org/ocre/>.
2. Click the 'Browse' button.
3. Familiarize yourself with the way in which types are described on OCRE.
4. There are many ways in which you can subdivide the 41,710 types listed on OCRE. Try to figure out which of the 'Refine results' options are most useful if you want to make smaller queries. This will be useful when we turn to [Steps 2-4](#).
5. In the following guide, we will only use the 'Search'-bar in the upper right corner of the blue toolbar, and filter our search results by means of the 'Refine results'-function. An alternative way is to delimit your queries from the start by using the more advanced 'Search'-function, the button for which can be found next to the 'Browse'-button. The options available here (visible to the right of this text) are generally the same as the ones you find under 'Filter results'.

Step 2: Searching and specifying your search results

1. Type 'Victory' in the search bar (upper right).
2. You may want to transfer your search results to a more comprehensible database. This can be done by means of CSV-files (to which we shall return during [Step 4](#)). However, these files can only contain 5,000 results at a time. Any query exceeding this number should therefore be filtered in one way or another. Find a way to lower the number of your current search results under 'Refine Results'.
3. When making your (for the moment hypothetical) database, you probably also want to include the results that disappeared after the refining of [Step 2.2](#). Do so by replacing the 'AND' in the URL of [Step 2.2](#) by 'NOT'. You could do this by using a new tab, as you may want to use your previous queries again during later steps (the same goes for when you further specify your query).
4. If during [Steps 2.2](#) and [2.3](#) you have chosen the right way of refining your results, you now have two queries below 5,000 results. If further delimitation of either of the two queries is required to export the results in CSV-files, return to either the 'AND'-query of [2.2](#) or the 'NOT'-query [2.3](#), and use 'Refine Results' to further delimit your query.

Note: sometimes the 'Refine Results' does not work properly when working with the 'NOT'-function. This may result in a query with, for example, all the coins with the portrait of Trajan instead of only those that are related to the term 'Victory'. In this case copy from the URL the text that follows upon '/results?q='. Then go to the previous page and first add '+AND+' or '+NOT+' to the URL of this page and then paste the copied text.

5. Do not forget to also include those results that were left out during [Step 2.4](#) by again changing 'AND' to 'NOT' for the new filter. You now have three separate queries ready to be transferred to Excel.
6. If for any of your queries your results still exceed 5,000, keep repeating [Steps 2.4](#) and [2.5](#) until all the separate queries are below 5,000.

Step 3: (Further) specifying your search results

1. Besides Victory, another personification closely associated with the emperor's fortunes on the battlefield is Virtus, who also commonly appeared on Roman imperial coins. It might thus be worthwhile to see the extent to which this is also reflected in imperial coinage: type 'Virtus' in the search bar.
2. For our database on the appearance of religious structures in Roman imperial coinage, we do not need the results that already include the term 'Victory', as we already found these during [Step 2](#). There are two ways to remove these results from your query. The first is to fill in 'Victory' under the heading 'Keyword' (and click the magnifying glass, not 'Refine Search'), and then change 'AND' in the URL to 'NOT'. The second way is to directly add '+NOT+fulltext%3AVictory' to the URL.

Note: here the results of the query are below 1,000, and thus easily exportable through CSV. If this would not have been the case, the 'Refine Results' option would again have done the trick, in the same way as during [Steps 2.2](#) and [2.4](#).

Appendix to Steps 2 and 3: Further tips and tricks

- You can also search for longer parts of the descriptions rather than key words, by placing the required text between “..” in the search bar below 'Keyword'. If for example you want to filter out obverses that show the portrait of Jupiter, fill in ““Head of Jupiter”” and repeat the 'AND'/'NOT' trick that you must be familiar with by now. Note, however, that terminology is not always the same in OCRE, so that you may want to use various synonyms to also remove similar results. In this case 'Bust of Jupiter' is an alternative.
- Sometimes you may want to search for shorter or longer forms of the same word. In that case use an asterisk (*) behind or in front of (part of) the term you place in the search bar. If, for example, you want to have a look at the appearance of soldiers on Roman coinage, the search term 'soldier*' will result in coins on which both single and multiple soldiers figure. Note that the same results will be found when using 'sol*' as a search term, albeit among the various other terms starting with 'sol-', such as *solidus* or the solar deity Sol himself.
- Sometimes you may want to search for various forms of the same word of the same length, especially when looking for different cases in coin legends. In this case use a question mark in the place of the letter(s) that may vary. If, for example, you want to compare the appearance of AVGVSTA to AVGVSTI and AVGVSTO, fill in 'AVGVST?' in the search bar . The '?' only works for single characters, so for AVGVSTVS/AVGVSTAE, the query 'AVGVST??' should be used instead.

1. Now let us turn to making an actual database. Use the results of [Steps 2 and 3](#), or think of a topic that suits your own interest, preferably one for which a (very) limited number of words is used on OCRE (as you have seen during [Step 1.3](#)).
2. If your query exceeds 1,000 coin types, you have to split the results as under [Step 2](#).
3. Use the CSV-button: the third button under 'Data Options' (upper left corner).

4. Import into Excel:
 - a. Open a new file.
 - b. Go to 'Data' => 'From Text'.
 - c. Select the query you just downloaded under [Step 4.3](#) from your 'Downloads' folder, then click 'Import'.
 - d. A window will pop up immediately. Given that the data of the CSV-file is divided by commas, select 'Delimited' in the Text Import Wizard, click 'Next', then deselect 'Tab' under the Delimiters and select 'Comma' instead (you will already see the Data preview change). Then click 'Finish'.

Note: if [Step 4.4d](#) did not yet result in separate columns, select the first column of the sheet by clicking on the 'A' above it, then go to 'Data' => 'Text to Columns'. The same window as under [4.4d](#) will pop up, and you should follow the same steps (select 'Delimited'; click 'Next'; deselect 'Tab'; select 'Comma'; click 'Finish'). This should do the trick. If it still does not work, call for your instructor.
5. If your overall query does not exceed 1,000 coin types, go to [Step 4.7](#), if it does:
 - a. Use the CSV-button for the results of the 'NOT'-query (if your first query was an 'AND'-query, otherwise do it the other way round).
 - b. Repeat [Step 4.4](#).
6. Copy-paste the results of [4.5b](#) (minus the headings) into the file of [Step 4.4](#).
7. Select the entire sheet and find the table-style of your preference under 'Home' => 'Format as Table'. The ones with the colored top row probably result in the more comprehensible tables.
8. Save your file: you now have your very own database.

Step 5: Using Excel to quantitatively assess your material

1. Use the database created under [Step 4](#).
2. Select the table by simply clicking one of its cells, and go to 'Insert' => 'PivotTable'. When a window pops up, make sure your table is selected under 'Select a table or range', and choose 'New Worksheet'. Click 'OK'.
3. Now an empty table will appear in a separate tab to which you are automatically directed. Let us first fill the 'VALUES'-area. 'URI', 'Title' and 'RecordId' are all unique identifiers of the coin types, so select one of these, and drag the heading from the PivotTable Fields into the 'VALUES'-area. Your Table will now show 'Count of ...' only.

Note: If instead of 'Count' the 'Sum' of the VALUES is shown left-click on 'Count of...' in the 'VALUES'- area and change the Value Field Settings.

Alternatively, you could double-left-click 'Count of ...' in the actual sheet and change 'Sum' to 'Count' in the 'Summarize Values By'-tab.

4. Next we would like to see the extent to which your theme appeared under a select number of emperors. Therefore, either tick the box before 'Authority' or drag this heading into the 'ROWS' area. You now most likely get a rather long list of emperors. To make it more comprehensible click the arrow next to the 'Row Labels' and select your preferred emperors (preferably those with numbers exceeding 10) in the drop-down menu that appears. You may want to change the alphabetical order into a chronological order by selecting both the name of an emperor and the adjacent number, left-clicking (and holding) the right border of the selected cells and then dragging them into the right position.
5. To see if we would get different results if we look at specific metals, drag 'Material' into the 'COLUMNS'-area.
6. To make the results visually more attractive, a graph could be useful. Make sure you select your table, go to 'Insert' => 'Recommended charts', and choose the graph of your liking. Given that the number of coin types vary heavily between the various reigns, the '100% Stacked Column' will probably be more useful than any of the other graphs for comparing between reigns the extent to which the appearance of (if you used the examples of [Steps 2 and 3](#) here) religious structures was distributed over the three metals.
7. Click on the graph and go to 'Design' to modify your chart in various ways (e.g. addition of numbers, changing colors).

1. Use the database created under [Step 4](#).
2. Add an extra column to the table by clicking your right mouse button anywhere in the table, then select 'Insert' => 'Table Columns to the Left'.
3. Think of a text-based question that can be answered either positively or negatively. This will be the 'topic' of this new column. An example question: does the reverse image contain a figure of Victory?
4. Select the arrow next to the title of the category you would like to analyze (e.g. Reverse type or Denomination), then go to 'Text Filters' => 'Contains.../'Does not contain...', and fill in the term you would like to filter in or out.
5. In your new column type 'Yes' or 'No' in the upper cell. Click on this cell, then click and hold the left mouse button on the lower right corner of this cell and scroll all the way down. Now all the cells corresponding to the filter have the same answer. Alternatively, select all the cells of the new column by clicking the letter above it and press 'Ctrl+F'. Choose 'Replace', leave 'Find what' open and type 'Yes' or 'No' in the 'Replace with'-section. Click 'Replace all'.
6. Fill in the opposite answer for the cells that you filtered out. This can be done by first deleting the Text Filter: use the same drop-down menu as under [Step 6.4](#), and click 'Clear Filter from ...'. Then use the 'Replace all' function as under [Step 6.5](#), but now for the opposite answer.
7. Now go to your PivotTable you made during [Step 5](#). Click the right mouse button while your cursor is placed within the table and click 'Refresh'.
8. Remove 'Material' from the 'COLUMNS'-area by dragging it into the 'FILTERS'-area instead (we will get to that in a bit).
9. Move the title of your newly created column now visible among the PivotTable Fields into the now empty 'COLUMNS'-area.
10. Create a chart to visualize your results as during [Step 5.6](#).
11. Since you dragged the 'Material'-category into the 'FILTERS'-area, you can now filter out the metals to see if significant changes occur when only focusing on (a combination of) gold, silver or bronze.
12. Obviously, you could also use different filters. Try 'Mint', for example, to see what happens if you only include the mint of Rome into your analysis.